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Military Veterans' Pathways from High School to Postsecondary Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the pathways of U.S. military veterans from high school to postsecondary engineering education. In the U.S., there is a growing demand for engineering professionals from diverse backgrounds. Given that many military veterans come from diverse backgrounds and some receive technical training while in the military, their participation in engineering education has great potential to contribute to expanding and diversifying the engineering workforce. This is a mixed methods case study that utilizes survey data and semi-structured interviews with 20 military veterans pursuing engineering degrees across four academic institutions in the U.S. Our analysis of the survey data reveals that student veterans in engineering (SVEs) take various paths as they embark upon their engineering studies. Thematic analysis of the in-depth interviews shows that SVEs pursue engineering based on numerous factors, including: early and life-long engineering interest, encouragement from veterans' centers, and the positive job outlook. This article presents four cases of participant pathways into engineering education. Research findings provide context and information regarding student veterans' pathways into engineering, revealing overlooked areas for promoting student veterans' participation in engineering as well as encouraging the development of new strategies to support student veterans' interest and success in engineering.

1 INTRODUCTION

There are numerous calls to increase participation in postsecondary engineering education in the U.S., and the veteran population is considered to be a tremendous resource for expanding and diversifying the engineering workforce [1]. Many U.S. colleges are enrolling an increasing number of veterans with an expected growth of 30% per year due to the expanded benefits of the Post-9/11 GI Bill, which covers the full cost of in-state tuition at public colleges, and the Yellow Ribbon Program, which provides additional financial assistance to attend private colleges, making postsecondary education affordable and accessible [1]. Although the number of military veterans pursuing higher education is increasing, a relatively lower proportion of them are pursuing engineering degrees specifically, despite often receiving technical training while in the military that aligns with these fields of study. This study examines the academic and military pathways of a group of military veterans who are pursuing bachelor's degrees in engineering. Using a mixed-methods case study approach across four institutions, we conducted an online survey and individual interviews to gain insights on the following research questions:

1. What are the academic and military pathways of student veterans pursuing engineering education?
2. How do military experiences contribute to their pathways into engineering?

We analysed the survey data using descriptive analysis and the interview data using thematic analysis and identified four different pathways from high school to postsecondary engineering education including the military and often work and other higher education. Our findings provide context and information for various applications, such as: 1) identifying ways in which the military can help separating

service members transition into engineering education; 2) developing new strategies to support student veterans as they plan and develop their academic and career trajectories; and 3) identifying potentially overlooked areas for promoting student veterans' participation in engineering in the U.S. Overall, we illustrate some of the paths that military veterans have taken to pursue engineering. We highlight their important stories to provide a guide for others to consider, as well as to identify areas that could be strengthened to facilitate transition into engineering specifically, and higher education, in general.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Since 2008, nearly 500,000 military veterans in the U.S. have used GI Bill Benefits to fund their education, and many college campuses across the nation are considering how best to serve the needs of this population [2]. Universities have increased their services for student veterans — constructing new centers to serve student veterans, augmenting campus advising services, offering early enrolment in courses to speed time to graduation, and strengthening other programming. To better inform the development of support programs for student veterans, particularly those interested in engineering, this study investigates the pathways of student veterans enrolled in engineering programs at four academic institutions.

The pathways of military veterans are complex because of several factors that distinguish their academic trajectory from traditional engineering students. There is often a gap between their high school studies and their pursuit of a Bachelor's degree. Given the relatively large cultural transition into college from the military, which provides more structure than civilian undergraduate life [3], student veterans face unique challenges. For one, student veterans are typically older and have a wider breadth of experiences than traditional-aged college students. They are also more likely to be first-generation students; that is, students whose parents did not earn a college degree or attend college [4]. Some first-generation students struggle because their academic pathways do not share the same access to social capital as their peers who come from households with college experience. Research has suggested, for example, that they may be stymied by lower educational aspirations and/or lower academic preparation [4, 5]. However, previous studies show that military training can provide motivation for academic success and more defined career paths [6]. Military training can also provide important skills useful for engineering study and professional practice, such as technical preparation [7], teamwork, communication, and leadership [4, 8, 14].

Students choose to major in engineering for many reasons including interest in the subject matter, previous academic experiences, and the hands-on opportunities that engineering provides [10]. Individual-level characteristics, such as engineering-related attainment value (“being an engineer is consistent with sense of self”) have been shown to be associated with higher interest in pursuing an engineering degree [9, p.299]. Although these studies were not focused on student veterans, student veterans may share some of these same reasons for pursuing engineering. The present study examines the pathways of student veterans into engineering and extends our previous research using focus groups to identify military veterans' pathways into engineering [11].

3 DATA AND METHODS

With Institutional Review Board approval, we conducted a mixed-methods case study to examine the academic and military pathways of student veterans pursuing Bachelor's degrees in engineering. Our sample for this paper is comprised of 20 student veterans across four academic institutions in the U.S, which we anonymize as Western University, Southern State, Midwest State, and Eastern University. The demographic characteristics of the student veterans we interviewed are presented in Table 1. Our sample is primarily composed of male, White Marine or Navy student veterans. Most are majoring in mechanical or electrical and computing engineering, which are also the largest enrolment engineering fields in the U.S. [15].

Interview participants completed an online survey that included questions regarding their demographic characteristics and academic and military trajectories between high school and postsecondary engineering education. We obtained data regarding our participants' trajectories using a "lifeline/life history" exercise, which asked survey respondents to identify at which age they engaged in or experienced the following activities: (1) graduated from high school, (2) joined the military, (3) served in the military, (4) attended classes, (5) left the military, (6) worked at a paid job outside of the military, and (7) attended college(s). The "lifeline/life history" exercise also included questions regarding time of marriage/divorce, birth/dependents, and service-related injury (if any were applicable), and provided open areas for respondents to add other major/significant life events. We generated an Excel chart to document the life history of each interview participant and conducted descriptive statistics on the relevant variables. We then created a visual display of qualitative information, which we coin as a "path diagram", for each participant, and subsequently compared these diagrams as a method for categorizing commonalities.

We complemented the survey data by conducting individual interviews with each of the student veterans in engineering (SVEs) using a semi-structured interview protocol. A professional transcriptionist transcribed the audio recording of the interviews, and we verified the accuracy of the transcripts through review. Our initial analysis of the data comprised re-reading the verified transcripts and writing an episode profile for each interview, which highlighted the key points and most compelling quotes in relation to the participants' military and academic pathways [12]. We also used the transcripts to verify the "life history" data provided in the survey. The interviews also provided elaboration on major life events, as well as reasons for the key transition events.

We then applied a three-step coding process comprised of open coding, axial coding, and selective coding [13] using NVivo 12, a qualitative data analysis program. For open coding, we identified the key themes related to academic and military pathways. For axial coding, we categorized these themes into the different categories of pathways. For selective coding, we connected the different pathways with one another. We compared the resulting themes and categories across and within participants, and connected the findings with the "life histories" as analysed from the survey data. We generated "case notes," which synthesized the "life history" and interview data focusing on how military experiences contribute to following the engineering path, using a representative participant from each identified pathway. The representative case for each pathway was selected in order to present a range of demographic backgrounds and engineering institutions.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Study Participants

Demographic Characteristics		n	%
Sex	Male	20	100%
Race	White	14	70%
	Black	4	20%
	Asian	1	5%
	Other	1	5%
Military Branch	Navy	9	45%
	Marine Corp	8	40%
	Air Force	2	10%
	More than 1	1	5%
Engineering Major	Mechanical	11	55%
	Electrical & Computing	4	20%
	Civil	2	10%
	Aerospace	1	5%
	Agriculture	1	5%
	Industrial	1	5%
Total		20	100%

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4 RESULTS

We identified four distinct pathways (A-D) among our 20 student veteran participants. Below we present each pathway using a representative case highlighting how the military contributed to the SVE’s pursuit of a bachelor’s degree in engineering.

4.1 Pathway A: Military, Work, and Higher Education before Engineering

Fig. 1. Pathway A: Military, Work, and Higher Education Before Engineering

Seven respondents’ pathways from high school to engineering followed that of Pathway A, where they began work soon after exiting the military and then attended a different higher education institution before pursuing their engineering degree. The representative case is Jonathan, a male, Asian American Marine studying mechanical engineering at Western University. Jonathan joined the military as soon as he graduated from high school. After serving for 4 years, he departed the military to work in his family’s business. During the nine years he worked in his family

business as a phone service technician, he also enrolled in a few classes at the local community college. During community college, he realized he wanted to become an engineer because of the support and encouragement he received from the campus Veterans' Success Center.

Jonathan shared,

“What really helped me was...I was introduced to the Veterans' Center, ... where you have friendly veterans willing to help... It was in the [community college] Veterans Center that... [a Marine] was openly talking about ‘[if] you're going to go to school, you might as well go into a degree plan that you are interested in because it doesn't matter how much the pay is if you don't like your job.’ I took that into consideration. I changed my degree to mechanical engineering.”

Whereas Jonathan previously thought of engineering as his hobby, his involvement with the Veterans' Center inspired him to pursue this program as a degree and to strive for higher grades in order to transfer into a four-year institution. His transition into the four-year Western University was facilitated by mentorship from another veteran who allayed his fears regarding the higher tuition. Although Jonathan did not feel that his transition to college was facilitated by the military or that his supervisors in the military actively encouraged him to pursue higher education, he received abundant mentorship from veteran peer mentors at the Veterans' Center at both higher education institutions he attended, which helped establish his pathway into engineering.

4.2 Pathway B: Military and Work before Engineering

Fig. 2. Pathway B: Military and Work Before Engineering

Of our 20 interview participants, only one followed this particular pathway of entering the workforce immediately after the military and then enrolling directly into a bachelor's degree program in engineering. Jesse is White, male, and served in the Navy. He is majoring in computer engineering at Southern State. After Jesse graduated from high school, he served in the military for 3 years. He then worked for 5 years in the private sector primarily on engineering projects. His company “identified [him] as a high-value asset. They didn't want to risk losing [him] to another company so they paired [him] up with a mentor.” His mentor encouraged him to pursue a degree in order to move up to management. Thus, Jesse decided to pursue a college degree, but he chose engineering because he has “always been along that engineering path” and “computers will always be [his] hobby and influence [his] life directly.”

Jesse intended to go directly to college from high school and was attending college orientation programs when he overheard his parents talking about the financial challenges of paying college tuition. It was then that he decided to join the military

instead because “it pays for college and you get a paycheck right away.” In the Navy, Jesse was a nuclear electronics technician, and that experience solidified his interest in engineering. After exiting the military, he worked as a control engineer, and his supervisor assigned him entry-level engineering work activities. However, without an engineering degree, he had limited opportunities for a promotion to management, and that compelled him to consider pursuing a bachelor’s degree. He said, “it was a fit. I was good in science and math in school, now I’m applying science and math in real life in my job, and I still like it.” And as Jesse described, he appears to have always been on the engineering path, although with stops in the military and in work, both of which solidified his interest in pursuing an engineering degree.

4.3 Pathway C: Higher Ed, Military, and Higher Ed Before Engineering

Fig. 3. Pathway C: Higher Ed, Military, and Higher Education Before Engineering

Seven of our respondents began higher education immediately after high school, but left college before graduating to join the military. Once exiting the military, they attended another higher education program before pursuing a Bachelor’s degree in engineering. Our representative case for Pathway C is Brian, who was a jet engine mechanic in the Air Force, and is now pursuing mechanical engineering at Southern State. Brian is male, Black, and started engineering at a postsecondary institution immediately after high school. Even though he wanted to join the military right out of high school, he received scholarships that encouraged him to pursue higher education instead; “Joining the military... was something that I wanted to do...straight out of high school...I had scholarships to [go to college]. So, it was like everyone expected me to do that. So, I just thought, ‘Well, I’ll just go to [college].” However, in his third year of undergraduate studies, Brian decided to join the military: “it finally got to the point where I was tired of school ... and I wanted to be productive...Joining the military...helped me meet a lot of people... guided me while I wasn’t in school and helped guide me back towards school.”

For Brian, his military service drew him away from undergraduate studies, but also gave him the depth of experience and connections he was looking for, as well as the motivation, to continue to finish his engineering degree. After the military, he attended a community college and then returned to Southern State where he first started his higher education before the military. He imagines that engineering has always been on his path, “I have an uncle who’s an engineer...And, I was like ‘Ok, all these guys are successful.’...’Let me go try engineering...’ People always told me, you like taking apart cars and all that stuff.” His military service gave him the opportunity to explore the world and different applications of engineering that he needed to solidify his commitment to finishing the engineering degree. It also helped

that when he returned to a bachelor’s engineering degree program after the military, Brian had a sibling at the same institution and that they gave him additional support and another reason to complete his degree.

4.4 Pathway D: Higher Ed and Military Before Engineering

Fig. 4. Pathway D: Higher Ed and Military Before Engineering

The five respondents who followed Pathway D started pursuing engineering degrees right after exiting the military. For Harry, a white, Male Marine now pursuing agricultural engineering at Midwest State, the military was a 20-year break from college. Harry initially enrolled at Midwest State after high school as an electrical engineering student. He said, “I was only 17, and prone to 17-year-old tendencies, and I didn’t do very well. I’ve always had the goal of coming back and becoming a [Midwest State] engineer.” Looking back, he said he decided to join the military because of the “college benefits that you could earn after service.”

“There was a very rich military tradition in my family. I’m actually a third-generation Marine. There’s lots of military in my family. I’ve always wanted to be a pilot. With doing all that, and a little bit of patriotic service, and getting college benefits, that made kind of a logical choice for me to go into the military.”

After 20 years serving in the military, Harry shared, “I’ve finished my career. I’ve found more personal enlightenment in being an outside naturalist. Wildlife is more happiness than monetary...I’m a little bit older. I had the chance to do something in wildlife and ecology, environmental science, and still be an engineer.” While in the military, Harry sought help in planning for returning to education, “There’s a section in the headquarters that dealt with education...and they would help you out with college degrees, and then there’s our separation class, where they help us transition from military to civilian life, and they connect us with the Department of Labour, Department of Defense, Veterans Affairs, entities that help you with your benefits and places that you can go to still get help.” In particular, because he wanted to make a career change from aviation maintenance to wildlife range management, “that program actually sat you down and helped you with what kind of degree you want.” Unlike Jonathan from Pathway A, Harry received a lot of support from the military in his transition into postsecondary engineering education. Military service helped him refine his career interests and identify an engineering path that would prepare him for a meaningful career. It also gave him the perspective and motivation he did not have at age 17 to pursue and complete an engineering degree, which was his life-long goal.

5 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Based on our interviews with 20 student veterans, we presented four pathway cases highlighting the stories of Jonathan, Jesse, Brian, and Harry. Those who travelled

on pathways A and B worked after exiting the military before pursuing engineering degrees, whereas those on pathways C and D started some form of higher education after exiting the military. Our case studies reveal that military service contributed to our student veterans' pathways into engineering in a variety of ways, beyond the financial support provided by the GI Bill and Yellow Ribbon programs. Whereas Jonathan (Pathway A) did not find that his supervisors in the military actively encouraged him to pursue higher education after separation, he did find a lot of support from other veterans through two different campuses with Veterans' Centers. His engagement with the Veterans' Centers reminded him of his interest in engineering and helped him identify engineering as a viable pursuit. In contrast, Harry (Pathway D), who served in the military for 20 years, found that his time in the military helped him gain the maturity, perspective, and skills to re-try obtaining his engineering degree, albeit in a different engineering discipline, from the same academic institution he started at when he was 17 years old. Becoming an engineer was his life-long goal and his military service helped make it a possibility, including through their provision of support services during the separation and transition period. Likewise, Brian (Pathway C) found that his military service provided him a much-needed break from his initial engineering studies and instilled in him the connections and perspectives he needed to be appropriately motivated to be successful in his second attempt at an engineering degree. Jesse (Pathway B), who pursued work then engineering after military service, also indicated that engineering has always been one of his goals. Military service made college affordable and also provided him with technical skills that made him invaluable to his employer, who encouraged Jesse to pursue a degree to be considered for a management position.

Overall, as exemplified by the four case studies presented, military service has contributed positively to our participants' pathways into engineering in the U.S. For all of them, it made college affordable and provided them with the skills, perspectives, connections, and motivation to actively pursue engineering. However, all of our case studies represent student veterans who have shown some interest in science and engineering prior to entering the military. Military service helped to further and solidify these interests, both directly and indirectly. Future research should examine the experiences of military veterans who may not have as strong existing connection with engineering prior to military service and explore how technical jobs in the military may contribute to potential interest in professional engineering practice. Our research findings provide important contextual information for student services centers and other groups and organizations supporting military veterans' transition into civilian life and into postsecondary education. Research findings also illustrate important stories that could potentially inform other military veterans about the multitude of pathways travelled and how some student veterans have leveraged their military service. While our study focuses on SVEs in the U.S., our findings have implications for academic institutions with non-traditional students in other countries. Support provided by academic institutions and from student peers make a difference in the academic trajectories of non-traditional students.

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